

THE ROLE OF COLLOCATIONS IN LANGUAGE LEARNING

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Abstract

The article studies collocations and its role in language learning and teaching. Collocations play a great role for enriching foreign language vocabulary. The role of its in natural speaking is irreplaceable. It helps you to speak fluently and accurately. It also develops your communication skills. Collocations impact understanding texts and getting their meaning easily. Relationship between grammatical structures and meaning is interesting part of the collocations. Collocations are sometimes mixed with idioms and slangs.

Keywords: collocation, natural language, combinations, expressions, grammatical structure

INTRODUCTION

In order to speak any foreign language fluently, it is important to have a rich vocabulary. Collocations are one of the means of enriching this vocabulary. If we use collocations correctly and in place, it will help us to have a good speaking ability. So let's see what collocation is. Collocations enrich expression and fluency and play an active role in communication with these aspects. The use of collocations affects language development and makes communication easier.

A collocation is a grouping of familiar words, especially words that usually appear together and thus convey meaning by association. The term collocation was first used in its linguistic sense by the British linguist John Rupert Firth, who noted, "You should be able to see a word by the company it keeps." A collocation range refers to the set of elements that usually accompany a word. The size of the collocational range is determined in part by the level of specificity of the word and the number of meanings.

In other words, Collocations are fixed phrases in English that are formed by the joint use of two or more words. These expressions have a different meaning than the meaning of single words and are richer and more precise than the meaning expressed by single words. For example, "make a decision" is more accurate than "do a decision". The phrase "do a decision" is incorrect and is not used in English. Collocations are important for language learners because they help learn the correct usage of the language.

MAIN PART

Types of collocations.

Collocations arise in different ways. Rather, it is formed from combinations of different parts of speech. The different types of collocations reflect the diversity of expressions used in the language. These types generally indicate which word types come together to form a natural expression and which grammatical structures are based on them. Here are some of the basic types of collocations:

1. Verb + Noun Collocations:

• In this genre, the use of certain verbs with certain nouns is typical. For example: we can say "have a party", "hold a party" and "throw a party". The meaning is the same. Similarly, we can say "do a test" (or exam), "take a test" (or exam) and "sit a test" (or exam). Or we can also say: [4]

Other examples:

Have a holiday

Have a rest

Have a problem

2. Adjective + Noun Collocations:

• Situations where certain adjectives are used with certain nouns. For example, expressions such as "strong coffee" and "heavy rain" can be given as examples of this category. [6]

Other examples:

Common knowledge

Common language

Deep feeling

3. Verb + Adverb Collocations:

• Expressions using a combination of verbs and adverbs. For example, expressions such as "run quickly" and "eat slowly" are examples of this type.

Other examples:

deeply regret

distinctly remember

firmly believe

4. Noun + Noun Collocations:

• Expressions where one noun is used with another noun. For example, expressions such as "car park" and "apple pie" are examples of this category.

Other examples:

A sense of pride.

Accounting system

A pang of nostalgia

5. Adjective + Adjective Collocations:

• Expressions using certain adjectives together. For example, expressions such as "happy-go-lucky" and "black and white" are examples of this type.

Other examples:

Absolutely necessary

Bitterly cold

Deeply hurt

6. Verb + Preposition Collocations:

• Expressions using certain verbs with certain prepositions. For example, expressions such as "depend on" and "deal with" are examples of this category.

Other examples:

Take care of

Hear of

Dream of

Expressions are sometimes confused with idioms and slangs. Idioms cannot be changed. Slangs may

sometimes bear a real meaning though in some cases they are used in an abstract sense [1, p.153].

When we approach the matter from stylistic point of view, euphemism and dysphemism can show themselves here. Babayev Javid gives such an example: "The late grandpa passed away after saying "Take care of yourselves" (euphemism) [2, p.12].

The Effect of Collocations in for natural speaking.

The use of collocations is important for natural speaking. Collocations are word pairs or groups that include grammatical structures and semantic components, increasing the fluency and naturalness of natural language. These structures, which are formed by combining words in a language according to a certain order or pattern, make communication more effective. While contributing to the natural fluency of the language, they stand out with the following aspects:

Meaning Integrity: Words generally gain meaning integrity when they come together in a certain order or pattern. For example, the word "strong" in the phrase "strong coffee" indicates that the coffee has a strong, intense, or tangy flavor. Such matches help to explain the meaning of the language and to understand the meaning more clearly.

Clarity of Expression: Using specific collocations can increase the clarity of expressions. For example, the phrase "make a decision" clearly expresses the action of making a decision. When such patterns are used, communication becomes more understandable.

Natural Language Usage: Collocations reflect the natural flow and everyday use of language. Combining certain words in a certain order provides a natural expression. This reflects real-life use of language, making communication more natural.

Word Choice and Ease of Construction: Using specific collocations provides clues about which words to use together when creating a phrase. This can simplify word choice and sentence structures when creating expressions.

Collocations contribute to the natural fluency of the language, making communication more understandable, clear and natural. It supports effective communication by reflecting the richness and depth of the language.

The role of collocation learning foreign language.

Collocations have a special role in second language learning. Let's say it more clearly collocations play a critical role in the language learning process because they are essential for understanding and adopting the fluency and usage of natural language.[7] These structures undertake the following roles in the language learning process:

Understanding Natural Language Usage:

Collocations are an essential tool for understanding how language is used. By learning these structures, students understand which words come together in a certain order and why they are used that way.

Deepening the Meaning: Collocations are a part of language where a certain combination of words creates special meanings. These structures deepen the meaning and increase the richness of the language.

Improving Grammar and Expression Ability: Understanding collocations supports grasping grammatical structures and constructing expressions more effectively. Putting words together in a certain order teaches students which word should be used in which situation.

Improving Natural Speaking and Writing Ability: Learning these structures gives students the ability to understand and use natural and commonly used expressions. This improves speaking and writing skills.

Effective Use of Language in Daily Life: Collocations help use language effectively in daily life. Learning these structures gives students a natural form of expression and makes them more comfortable communicating in real life. Collocations have an important role in the language learning process. These structures form a critical foundation for understanding, expressing, and using language effectively. In the language learning process, understanding and using collocations helps students improve their language skills

The role of collocation in communication

Collocations play an important role in communication. Here we can see the role of collocations in communication:

Clarifying the Meaning: Collocations are special meaningful expressions formed by combining certain words with others. Such structures clarify the meaning and enable more specific, clear expressions to be used. For example, collocations such as "take a risk", "make a decision" increase the openness of communication.[5]

Natural and Fluent Expression: Collocations reflect the natural use of language and increase the fluency of expressions. Using certain words in a certain pattern or order makes expressions more natural and fluent. This helps communication be more fluid and understandable.

Emotional and Discourse-Focused Expression:

Collocations sometimes reflect emotional or discourse-oriented use of language. For example, the phrase "catch someone's eye" is used in an emotional context, enriching communication.

Richness of Expression: Collocations help enrich expressions. It provides a wide vocabulary to express a particular situation, feeling or idea. They can be used to add different tones, emphasis or meaning in communication.

Effective and Clear Communication: Collocations encourage effective use of language and make communication more understandable. By making the right combinations of the right words, the message becomes clear and communication becomes stronger. Collocations, with their role in communication, enable expressions to be more effective, clear and natural. These structures contribute to making communication richer and more understandable by increasing the power and expressive ability of the language.

The Effect of Collocations in Texts

Collocations have a very important impact on texts and play a big role in the understandability, fluency and impressiveness of texts. Here is the effect of collocations in texts:

Enriching the Meaning: Collocations enrich the meaning in texts. Special combinations of certain words make the text deeper, clearer and more under-

standable. This ensures that the author can clearly convey the intention and content of the text to the reader. [5]

Fluency and Naturalness: Collocations increase the fluency of the text. The right combinations of certain words make the text sound more natural and fluid. This allows the reader to understand the text more easily and continue reading.

Effective Expression and Emphasis: Collocations can be used to emphasize certain situations or emotions. By using certain collocations, the author can place emphasis or express certain emotional tones in the text. This increases the impact of the text.

Enriching the Expression: Writers can enrich their expressions by using collocations in texts. The use of different collocations increases the expressiveness of the text and prevents it from becoming monotonous.

Connecting with the Reader: The use of collocations in texts can help establish a stronger connection with the reader. Natural and commonly used collocations allow the reader to become more engaged with the text. [7]

Reducing Semantic Complexity: When collocations are used to express a particular term or concept in texts, they can reduce semantic complexity. The use of specific collocations makes terms or concepts in the text more understandable.

Collocations are important linguistic elements that greatly affect the meaning, fluency and impact of texts. Writers' careful consideration when choosing a particular grammatical pattern or word combination can help them increase the impact of their texts and create a stronger connection with readers.

Grammar and Meaning Relationship of Collocations.

Collocations have a close relationship between grammatical structures and meaning. While grammar determines how words come together and how they are used, collocations refer to the combination of words in a specific order. In this context, the relationship between the grammar and meaning of collocations can be explained in the following ways: [3]

Grammar and Structural Relationship: Collocations form grammatical structure. The combination of certain words in a certain order or pattern reflects the rules of grammar. For example, some verb-object collocations determine what kinds of objects the verb will be used with. It refers to a specific combination of words based on a grammatical structure.

Determining Meaning: Collocations determine meaning within a particular grammatical structure. The use of certain words in a certain order or order conveys a specific meaning. For example, the combination of the words "make" and "decision" in the expression "make a decision" means to decide. In this context, grammatical structure determines collocations that convey a particular meaning.

Deepening the Meaning: Collocations emphasize the relationship between words and deepen the meaning. Especially when combined, these collocations express a particular meaning, emotion, or concept in a richer and more detailed way. By using certain words together, the meaning becomes more specific.

Natural Fluency of Language: Collocations ensure the natural fluency of the language. The combination of certain words in a certain order reflects natural and common usage. This supports the fluent and natural use of the language in daily life. Collocations are in a close relationship with grammatical structures and help deepen the meaning, express a certain meaning and ensure the natural fluency of the language. This relationship between grammar and meaning shapes the use and meaning of certain groups of words.

CONCLUSION

Collocations are important grammatical structures that deepen the natural fluency and meaning of the language. They have a critical role in the language learning process, communication and natural use of language. For students and language learners, learning and understanding collocations has these important implications:

Natural Language Fluency: Understanding collocations provides students with the opportunity to learn and adapt natural language use. These structures reflect the fluency and naturalness of everyday language.

Effective Communication: Using correct collocations makes communication more effective and understandable. Deepening and clarifying meaning strengthens communication.

Development of Grammar and Expression Skills: Understanding collocations supports grasping grammatical structures and creating expressions more effectively. This also improves language skills.

Usage in Daily Life: Knowing collocations enables understanding and using the natural use of language in daily life. This helps to become more comfortable and confident in communicating in real life.

As a result, collocations deepen the naturalness, fluency and meaning of the language. Learning these structures during the language learning process is an important part of improving language skills and communicating effectively. These structures are indispensable for understanding the real-life use and meaning of language.

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